

Digital Twins for Security-based Assurance of Edge-Cloud Software – a Data Platform Approach

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Abstract—This paper presents a conceptual view on a data platform of a distributed digital twin (DT) architecture for edge-cloud software systems, of which entities are provided and built by multiple stakeholders in a supply chain. We focus on exploring data platform approaches for DTs to support security-based assurance development and operation activities in an integrated manner by considering a holistic view of data, AI/ML models and service-based components as part of the edge-cloud software.

I. INTRODUCTION

In software development and operations, digital twins (DTs) have increasingly been explored for understanding and guaranteeing security and assurance of diverse types of entities in a complex software system [1]. We are interested in investigating how DTs can be used for facilitating security-based assurance [2] from the left – development activities – to the right – the operation activities – for IoT- and AI/ML- intensive software systems in edge-cloud continuum. Three crucial aspects are:

- Security from left to right: we cover the supply chain with multiple stakeholders that address security-based assurance by connecting the development to the operations using the data layers across different (virtual) DTs-like viewpoints of those stakeholders.
- IoT/AI-intensive software: we consider IoT data, AI/ML models and AI services as critical entities in modern software, besides common software components and services.
- Edge-cloud continuum: we have software systems developed and operated in edge-cloud continuum infrastructures with diverse types of network connectivity, runtime platforms, and computing resource providers.

This position paper discusses an approach to addressing the DTs for security-based assurance from data platform viewpoints. We consider the need to identify important types of data, exchange mechanisms, and edge data lakes for DT-enabled security-based assurance.

II. CONCEPTUAL MODELS

A. Software systems views, entities and stakeholders

Given an edge-cloud software, we consider the supply chain of the software with many aspects centered around: (i) data – for training AI/ML models as functionalities of the software or for analyzing the software security and assurance behaviors, (ii) AI/ML models – for offering functionalities of the software, (iii) software components including components with AI/ML models as the core feature – acting as

building blocks of the software, and (iv) software services – offering APIs for the software to use. Previous works have illustrated key entities in software chain [3]. But they miss key entities about data and AI/ML models, subsequently AI/ML-intensive components and services in the software. For DTs of such software, to emphasize the roles of data and AI/ML models in the IoT/AI-intensive edge-cloud software, we briefly analyze key stakeholders related to data and AI/ML models and services that are considered indispensable parts of the software in today’s edge-cloud continuum. Figure 1 provides a summarized view for stakeholders and workflows in making AI/ML components. For AI/ML service components and the services created from the components, most software developers and providers in the right side of the supply chain will develop or use existing AI/ML models based on pretrained ones and existing datasets. Therefore, if these developers and providers offer a service leveraging AI/ML models as a core functionality, it is crucial to manage trained models and datasets from various stakeholders outlined in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Key entities, stakeholders and workflows in making AI/ML models and components.

Combining the view in Figure 1 with the contemporary view of software supply chains, a high-level view of the left-to-right chain for IoT- and AI/ML-intensive software in edge-cloud continuum is depicted in Figure 2. For security-based assurance supports, from the left to the right, we explain key entities as follows.

Data resource. represents datasets as data resources for training AI/ML models used within the software and for decision making related to the operation of the software.

Workflow resource. represents specifications of workflows or workflow programs which are used in building datasets, AI/ML models and software components.

Software component. represents well-known types of software components, e.g., libraries, frameworks, standalone exe-

cutables, containers, and service-based components.

Service. represents services which are instantiated from service-based components or cloud/platform services for the software. They run continuously, being accessed via APIs.

Data Provider. performs data collection and preprocessing and provides the data for training. Data can be offered through data marketplaces or special mechanisms.

AI/ML Model Provider. performs training of the AI/ML models and provides pretrained models for fine-tuning models that other stakeholders can buy or use.

Software Provider. builds a software system and provides the software. In doing so, it can develop in-house components, data, and AI/ML models as well as can buy them and do further work, like integration with third party services.

Software Operator. deploys and operates a complete software system, which is an edge-cloud software system together with relevant edge-cloud infrastructural/platform resources and third parties services.

B. Individual digital twins for stakeholders and data sources

Each stakeholder can have its own DT, e.g., for monitoring and managing the stakeholder's data, models and components. Such an assumption is based on various work [4]. Different stakeholders may use similar DT systems; they may not have any DT but still manage various types of data to support their activities. However, there is no exchange of data at the moment through a coordinated and integrated platform or DTs. Given a complex software system, each stakeholder only sees a part of the software based on a partial view of the supply chain.

C. Exchange data for security-based assurance

Regardless of using DTs or not, in the view of a global software supply chain, there are implicit and explicit ways to exchange data among stakeholders. These types of data are needed for testing, evaluating, and monitoring security-based assurance requirements. In the context of DTs, data must be exchanged to relevant stakeholders without disclosing internal, sensitive data, e.g., by adopting the IDSA (<https://internationaldataspaces.org>). Different types of data can have different policies for data update frequency and freshness. For the purpose of security and assurance, important types of data that can be shared via and analyzed within DTs are:

Data entities from the Data Provider. Both datasets and metadata about datasets can be shared for security-based assurance; they are especially important in the age of AI with many emerging security issues and compliance regulations. Datasets can be shared using suitable mechanisms such as streaming or batching ingestion to data lakes. Many types of metadata are related to data regulation, quality of data, and governance. While a stakeholder's internal processes are complex and the stakeholder can have many sources of metadata, DTs require only needed data for the purpose of left-to-right security-based assurance that the stakeholder can extract and share. Currently, there is no standard or agreement about the types of metadata but various best practices do exist for consideration, like data resources [5] and datasheets for datasets [6].

Training workflows and AI/ML models from the AI/ML Model Provider. Security and assurance evaluation can also assess workflows for training AI/ML models, metadata about AI/ML models [7], and quality attributes. However, currently there is no standard of exchange models for such data, and the official channels for exchanges are not defined.

Bill of materials, and vulnerability and security reports from AI/ML Model and Software Providers. There are several well-known, common types of data describing the structure of software and AI/ML components for security and assurance, such as SBOM [8], AIBOM [9], and bug reports.

Testing data from the AI/ML Model and Software Providers. Testing data is also a source for finding non-compliance causes and providing evidence of security and assurance problems. Testing activities generate a huge amount of data and not all of them are suitable for sharing. In a software supply chain, at least two levels of testing data can be used: high-level testing reports and low-level testing datasets. Testing reports are mostly in report documents, but low-level testing datasets, which must be shared, are usually large.

Observability data from the Software Operator. Observability data acts as evidence and sources for analytics and detection. During the operations, various observability tools have been employed, such as Prometheus, Grafana, and Open-Telemetry [10]. Currently, highly common data, like telemetry traces and log data, are available and can be extracted from the observability. Furthermore, many observability tools provide streaming connectors and Agentic AI protocols (e.g., MCP) for receiving and querying monitoring data.

III. ARCHITECTURE – A CONCEPT DESIGN

Our proposed conceptual architecture is shown in Figure 3. In this paper, we focus on the lower part – the data plane – which supports data gathering and exchanges. The upper part of analytics and coordination is not presented. We outline main designs of the data gathering and exchanges as follows.

Extensible, cooperative, non-centralized DTs. Each stakeholder has its own business and it is possible to enable a virtual data space for all stakeholders involved. For simplicity, we present only one-to-one DT connections and exchanges. In this view, a stakeholder can enable possible connections to connect to another DT to receive the needed data. When related stakeholders do not have a DT, a stakeholder can still provide connections for the other stakeholders to request, ingest and share suitable data for the DT. Among stakeholders we expect the Software Provider and the Software Operator will have the most complex data and analytics features.

Data exchanges and schemas. There is no standard for many types of expected data, as well as it is not possible to impose standardized data models related to the semantics of data, AI/ML models and software components. Still best practices and widely used types of data can be agreed. Table I presents possible schemas selected for our designs.

Unified namespace and software structure dependencies. To organize information about stakeholders and relevant data of existing entities for DTs, we follow the unified namespace

Fig. 2: A high level view of the left-to-right chain for IoT- and AI-intensive software systems in edge-cloud continuum

Fig. 3: High level view of the distributed digital twins with two layers: Twin Data Platform and Twin Analytics and Coordination.

Type	Schemas
Various datasets, e.g. telemetry, logs, and testing data	dependent on the types of data, in CSV, JSON, AVRO, etc. via batch and streaming ingestions
Metadata for datasets	data resources models, datasheets for datasets
AI/ML models	model cards, Model Registry data (e.g., MLflow and AWS SageMaker)
Software package information and changes	SBOM, SPDX, AIBOM, C4, TOSCA
Bugs, CVEs, cyber threat intelligence	IEEE 1044-2009, Github Bug Report, MITRE CVE, STIX
Certificates and audit reports	ISO 27001, SLSA, and dependent on certified organizations

TABLE I: Supporting schemas for exchanged data

concept in data platforms [11]. DTs have a unified namespace for each software system to maintain information about stakeholders, which kind of data the stakeholders can provide, and the data associated with entities of a software system. A software system is modeled by using well-known techniques like component dependencies using SBOM, AIBOM and C4. **Connectors.** Diverse types of connectors are used for exchanging data, including requests for new data and updates. They will support different APIs and data formats. Most types of data updates in DTs are small in security and assurance analytics. Thus, they can be supported by streaming or batch-based connectors, such as REST uploading APIs. However, the testing and observability data can be voluminous, requiring different connectors for ingestion, such as based on object

storage. Similar to data platforms, we can have REST, Kafka, AMQP, and Agentic AI (e.g., MCP) -based connectors. Existing data space connectors (e.g., EDC Connectors – <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/Connector>) can also be integrated.

Edge data lake. An edge data lake is used for managing data within a DT. Going beyond traditional DTs, we have various types of data, requiring a stronger storage to support both files and objects. Naturally a data lake is a suitable one. In case of evidences from runtime and testing, large datasets can be supported. To design an edge data lake is also suitable for stakeholders. Edge computing systems can support better sovereignty and sensitive data protection and can leverage powerful edge hardware (e.g., NVIDIA DGX Spark) for complex analytics. Edge data lake can be designed with lightweight data technologies at the edge using DuckDB, Iceberg tables, and Polars [12].

Data pull and ingestion scheduling. When potential security and assurance issues occur and data are available for exchange, common scheduling methods (immediate or scheduled push/pull) can be used. However, the availability of data and the triggers of issues may not be made automatically, but through a human-in-the-loop in the stakeholder’s internal processes. For certain cases, with well-defined analytics in each DT/stakeholder, automatically updates can be pushed. Scheduling methods will be used by advanced coordination

techniques for security-based assurance analytics, e.g., during the compliance evaluation by humans or intelligent agents.

Data quality, freshness, up-to-date and conflicts. We do not expect to have big, near real-time data. One important aspect is to configure update frequencies and triggers within each DT to make sure that critical problems and data can be propagated according to the requirements. However, it is also important to provide safeguards against fall alarms. Based on the data platform approach, it is possible that each DT receives different data of the same entity from different DTs. While we can resolve this conflict using data engineering techniques, DT can also store the conflicting data and let the human experts and DT analytics agents and services to resolve the conflict.

Supports for end-to-end workflow analytics and responses. We expect to have many different mechanisms for security/assurance responses and coordination. Coordinating tasks for an assurance check is different from informing relevant stakeholders to provide additional data for the check. Visualization of the software can also require detailed data, AI/ML model, components, services and their execution environments, such as Kubernetes, containerized-based environments.

IV. FURTHER RELATED WORK

DTs for software engineering. The work in [13] presents a vision on using DT for software engineering processes, covering both activities in development and operations. It mainly discusses the activities and benefits, but does not focus on security-based assurance, supply chains, and architectural designs. The work in [14] is focused on DTs for system engineering, which is quite different from the goal of our DTs.

Software engineering for DTs. Many papers present software engineering techniques for DTs [15], [16]. The paper [17] proposes MDE as the approach for building DTs. Our approach is different, based on data platforms due to the various types of data that must be integrated for security-based assurance. The paper [18] presents a design framework for DTs and some use cases. However, it does not focus on a supply chain with data and AI/ML models and security/assurance cases.

Federated DTs. Other domains have proposed federated DTs [19], which are strong collaborative, tightly coupled DTs. The software supply chain and ecosystem have certain agreements in terms of sharing data for security and assurance, but they are not operational under a single stakeholder. Thus, practically we do not think that a strict federated DT model will be suitable. While the work in [20] is related, its context is for a project where stakeholders can have some short-term and strong data sharing for making the project work.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Addressing DTs for security and assurance with multiple stakeholders providing data, AI/ML models, components and the whole software in the supply chain requires fundamental work in data gathering and exchanges. We propose to focus on gathering data based on data platform principles, edge data lakes, and collaborative processes across different stakeholders. Our future work is to detail the design and implementation.

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